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FREE ECONOMIC ZONES AND FOREIGN INVESTMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the positive and negative factors associated with the operation of free economic zones (FEZs). It is argued that the provision of various tax, customs, and preference benefits often serves as a means of covert subsidization for certain lobby groups, as well as a means of initial capital accumulation. When assessing the impact of FEZs on a country's economic development, it is necessary to consider the presence of a favorable investment climate.

Key words: free economic zones, financial measures, fiscal methods, tax measures, non-financial incentives, offshore zones, investment climate, foreign capital.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada erkin iqtisodiy zonalar (EIZ) faoliyati bilan bog'liq ijobiy va salbiy omillar ko'rib chiqiladi. Turli soliq, bojxona imtiyozlarini taqdim etish ko'pincha ma'lum lobbi guruhlari uchun yashirin subsidiyalash vositasi, shuningdek, dastlabki kapital to'plash vositasi bo'lib xizmat qilishi ta'kidlanadi. EIZlarning mamlakat iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ta'sirini baholashda qulay investitsiya muhitining mavjudligini hisobga olish kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: erkin iqtisodiy zonalar, moliyaviy choralar, fiskal usullar, soliq choralari, moliyaviy bo'lmagan rag'batlantirish, ofshor zonalar, investitsiya muhiti, xorijiy kapital.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются положительные и отрицательные факторы, связанные с функционированием свободных экономических зон (СЭЗ). Отмечается, что предоставление различных налоговых и таможенных льгот нередко служит скрытым инструментом субсидирования отдельных лоббистских групп, а также средством первоначального накопления капитала. При оценке влияния СЭЗ на экономическое развитие страны необходимо учитывать наличие благоприятного инвестиционного климата.

Ключевые слова: свободные экономические зоны, финансовые меры, фискальные методы, налоговые меры, нефинансовые стимулы, офшорные зоны, инвестиционный климат, иностранный капитал.

INTRODUCTION

The efficient use of natural resources is not a sufficient condition for sustainable economic growth and, in some cases, merely distracts from addressing the core problems of economic development. Therefore, one of the most important objectives remains economic restructuring and the creation of industrial sectors capable of producing high-quality goods that are in strong demand.

The problems that arise in the process of establishing and operating free economic zones (FEZs) are complex and require the resolution of organizational, regulatory, economic, and methodological issues.

Developing scientific and methodological support for selecting regions and candidates for the establishment of FEZs, defining the rules for applying tax and other incentives for resident enterprises, and identifying their potential to enhance operational efficiency make it possible to take more well-founded decisions regarding the feasibility of creating such zones.

Enterprises operating within FEZs can stimulate other economic entities in related sectors and thereby improve the socio-economic situation in regions where FEZs are actively being established.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Scientific research on regional development issues and the role of investment in these processes is highly significant from both theoretical and practical perspectives. When examining the level of research on this topic, the existing literature can be broadly divided into three groups.

The first group includes general methodological works by well-known foreign authors such as K. Marx, M. Weber, J. Habermas, I. Wallerstein, T. Parsons, É. Durkheim, N. Smelser, and R. Swedberg, as well as

works by Russian scholars in economic sociology, including T. I. Zaslavskaya, R. V. Ryvkina, G. N. Sokolova, Yu. V. Veselova, V. V. Radaev, V. I. Verkhovina, I. L. Ryazantsev, M. S. Khalikov, and others. The second group comprises studies on regional development problems by authors such as N. N. Nekrasov, A. G. Granberg, T. G. Morozova, V. S. Bilchak, V. F. Zakharov, Yu. N. Gladkiy, G. V. Cherkashin, N. I. Larin, A. A. Kiselnikova, V. G. Ignatova, V. I. Butov, and others. The third group includes specialists studying the investment climate in regions, mainly economists and sociologists, such as V. N. Leksin, A. N. Shvetsov, V. V. Kotilko, I. I. Sanin, V. P. Oreshin, and others.

Uzbek economists Ermakhmudov, G. A. Melibayeva, and A. A. Isadjanova have examined the role of free economic zones in attracting foreign investment, drawing on global economic practices, international experience, international standards, and the methods used to regulate them.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article employs a systems approach, comparative analysis, generalization, structural-functional analysis, and sociological analysis methods.

Analysis and results

A universal set of measures is applied to attract foreign capital, including tax, financial, and non-financial (organizational) incentives. Despite certain differences in approaches to assessing economic measures that affect the interests of foreign investors, their essence lies in creating more favorable conditions in free economic zones (FEZs) compared to other territories.

In most FEZs operating worldwide, financial and non-financial incentives and conditions for investors include the following:

- exemption from customs duties and other charges on equipment, raw materials, and components imported into FEZs and used in the production of goods, primarily for export;
- exemption of companies from income tax (corporate tax), as well as other taxes and fees levied in a particular host country, for a sufficiently long period (from 5 to 10 years);
- reduction of tax rates for investors after the expiration of the so-called tax holiday period;
- exemption of reinvested profits from taxation;
- easing restrictions on the transfer of profits and capital abroad, including the abolition of taxes on profits remitted overseas;
- provision of preferential loans to regional investors, which is considered a more attractive incentive than tax benefits;
- provision of infrastructure services (energy, water supply, sewerage, transport, communications), land leases, and production facilities at preferential tariffs and prices.

Many FEZs in developing countries offer investors special exchange rate regimes. Among the incentives provided to investors in numerous FEZs in developing economies is also a special labor regulation regime, which generally corresponds to limited social protection.

An analysis of measures to ensure a favorable investment climate shows that a preferential tax system plays a central role in attracting foreign capital to free economic zones.

The establishment of offshore zones is mainly associated with two factors: proximity to business centers and the lack of internal resources for development.

According to the first factor, offshore centers emerged in regions of industrially developed countries such as the United States, Canada, Switzerland, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom.

The second factor led to the emergence of offshore centers in island states of the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans as a means of attracting foreign capital. Moreover, for many countries, income from offshore business constitutes a major source of revenue. The primary purposes of establishing offshore companies usually include reducing taxes, accelerating and simplifying international financial transactions, and increasing institutional confidentiality.

Recently, European offshore companies have gained an additional advantage. Unlike companies in classic zero-tax jurisdictions, which do not have such an identifier, all European offshore companies are assigned a single registration number upon incorporation [4]. Offshore companies are also used to transfer funds from company assets to the personal assets of company managers or owners. Depending on the jurisdiction, companies are divided into two groups:

1. offshore companies;
2. companies operating under preferential tax regimes.

Naturally, there is an ongoing international effort to combat money laundering and illegal human trafficking. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions in which various forms of zonal incentives in regions are applied not only to allocate them to specific companies, industries, or territories, but also to ensure that they become

effective instruments of economic modernization and tools for attracting investment to regions. Thus, the development of zones often goes beyond the initial plans that typically aim to address multiple objectives. Consequently, to maximize positive effects, it is essential to clearly define regional and sectoral priorities for the use of external resources [2].

China's experience shows that, at the initial stage, the number of FEZs should be limited, their scale compact, and their sectoral priorities clearly defined.

Principles of Forming Free Economic Zones:

When planning free economic zones (FEZs) and determining their specialization, it is necessary to analyze their international competitiveness in comparison with other FEZs located in different regions of the world. It should be borne in mind that the establishment of FEZs is a highly capital-intensive process [6].

To attract foreign capital, a set of infrastructure development measures is required. These measures should be based on the level of infrastructure services achieved in developed countries. It is essential to strike a balance between centralized regulation and local regional initiatives in favor of increasing autonomy for free economic zones.

The system of benefits and incentives contained in regulations must be aligned with international standards [3]. At the same time, it should be strictly tailored to the objectives set for FEZs, while remaining easy to implement and stable over the long term.

The regional and national economic effects of socio-economic impacts must be taken into account. If a certain number of FEZs are achieved alongside internal economic stability, these effects will be positive. The economic activities of FEZs should be carried out in accordance with the country's general legislation, with certain adjustments introduced to establish preferential regimes for investors.

This does not require the introduction of a national currency specific to FEZs or the establishment of a separate special economic legal framework. At the same time, it is important to recall the most typical negative aspects of foreign entrepreneurs' behavior in FEZs [5]. First, this includes the reluctance of foreign investors to make large long-term capital investments, resulting in a high degree of import dependence. Second, it involves policies of concealing profits through intra-company trade in components, that is, through transfer pricing.

The establishment of free economic zones is of great importance for the further development of the national economy, its economic indicators, and the diversification of the national economic structure. Through free economic zones, a country produces competitive products for global markets and attracts advanced foreign equipment and technologies, production lines and modules, as well as innovative technologies [7].

At present, numerous decrees and orders aimed at further developing this sector have been adopted. In accordance with a Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, free economic zones have been established in three regions of the country in recent years—Urgut, G'ijduvon, and Hazorasp. This demonstrates the significant attention being paid to this sector [8].

All free economic zones currently operating in Uzbekistan (Table 1):

Table 1. Free Economic Zones Operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Free Economic Zones (FEZs)	Free Economic Zones (FEZs)
Navoi FEZ	Zomin-Farm FEZ
Angren FEZ	Kosonsoy-Farm FEZ
Jizzakh FEZ	Sirdaryo-Farm FEZ
Kokand FEZ	Qoraqalpogiston FEZ
Namangan FEZ	Andijon-Farm FEZ
Khazorasp FEZ	Chiroqchi FEZ
Termez FEZ	Sirdaryo FEZ
Nukus-Farm FEZ	Tashkent FEZ
Fergana FEZ	Bukhara FEZ
Kashkadarya FEZ	Samarkand FEZ

A free economic zone is developed in accordance with a program approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Investments in free economic zones (FEZs) are increasingly becoming a popular method of attracting capital and promoting economic development in various regions of the world.

FEZs are specially designated areas within a country that facilitate economic activity and investment. They are established to stimulate regional development, attract investment, create new jobs, and enhance the overall competitiveness of the national economy.

Free economic zones typically offer investors a range of preferential conditions, including tax incentives, exemptions from customs duties, simplified procedures for obtaining construction permits, as well as access to infrastructure and technological platforms. These measures help reduce risks for investors and increase their returns, making FEZs attractive for business activity.

Investing in free economic zones can be beneficial for both domestic and foreign investors. For domestic companies, FEZs provide favorable opportunities to expand their businesses, access new markets and technologies, and improve competitiveness in the global market. For foreign investors, FEZs offer unique opportunities to enter the market, utilize local resources and skilled labor, and gain access to foreign markets and partners.

Investments in free economic zones have a positive impact on regional economies by contributing to job creation, infrastructure development, improvements in living standards, technological advancements in production, and export promotion. In addition, investments in special economic zones facilitate technology transfer and support the development of research, education, and healthcare sectors.

Investments in free economic zones represent an attractive opportunity for both investors and regions. They stimulate economic development and create conditions for sustainable economic growth, thereby making FEZs an important instrument for attracting investment and fostering regional development.

Summarizing the above research and analysis, it can be stated that the largest share of foreign direct investment is directed to free economic zones, as different regions of the country offer varying incentives and advantages. Therefore, the effective functioning of free economic zones and the volume of attracted foreign investment are directly interrelated.

Taking into account the current situation and influencing factors, it is advisable to implement the following measures to further increase the volume of foreign investment:

- further enhancing the investment attractiveness of free economic zones;
- improving banking activities;
- expanding the scope of medium- and long-term investment programs.

If the above recommendations are implemented, the volume of investment in the country will increase, thereby strengthening the competitiveness of the national economy.

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